

Ruthenium(III) mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium – A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Abstract : The oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) has been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at 298 K at constant ionic strength of 1.6 mol dm^{-3} . A minute amount of ruthenium(III) ($10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) is sufficient to enhance the slow reaction between succinic acid and cerium(IV). The main reaction products are cerium(III) and oxaloacetic acid. The stoichiometry is 1 : 4, that is $[\text{suc. acid}] : [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 1 : 4$. The reaction is first order in both cerium(IV) and ruthenium(III) concentrations. The order with respect to succinic acid concentration varies from first order to zero order, as the succinic acid concentration increases. Increase in sulphuric acid concentration decreases the reaction rate. The added sulphate and bisulphate decreases the rate of reaction. The added product cerium(III) retards the reaction rate. The active species of oxidant and catalyst are $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ respectively. Possible mechanism is proposed. The activation parameters were determined with respect to slow step and reaction constants involved have been determined.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, succinic acid, cerium(IV), ruthenium(III).

Introduction

Succinic acid (Butanedioic acid) is mainly used as flavoring agent for food and beverages, producing heterocyclic compounds, intermediate for dyes, perfumes, photographic chemicals, plasticizers, vehicle water cooling systems, medicines of sedative, antispasmodic, antiepileptic, antiparasitic and cancer curing.

Ruthenium(III) is an efficient catalyst in many redox reactions¹ involving different complexities due to the formation of intermediate complex, free radicals and multiple oxidation state of ruthenium^{1,2}. Cerium is a well known oxidant³ in acid media having reduction potential⁴ of the couple $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}$ at 1.70 V and is stable only in high acid concentration. In sulphuric acid and sulphate media, several sulphate complexes^{3,5} of cerium(IV) form, but their role has not received much attention so far. The oxidation of organic compounds by cerium(IV) in general, seem to proceed via the formation of an intermediate complex⁶. The slow reaction between succinic acid and cerium(IV) is mediated by a minute ($10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) amount of ruthenium(III) in aqueous sulphuric acid. The mechanism may be quite complicated due to the formation of different cerium(IV) complexes in the form of ac-

tive species. Literature survey indicates that, there is no reports on the ruthenium(III) mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV). Hence, we have investigated the ruthenium mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in order to understand the behavior of active species of oxidant in sulphuric acid media and to propose a suitable mechanism.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

Different sets of concentrations of reactants in 0.50 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid at constant ionic strength, 1.60 mol dm^{-3} and at constant catalyst, $5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ were kept for over 8 h at 25°C in a closed container. When $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] > [\text{suc. acid}]$ the remaining cerium(IV) was assayed by measuring the absorbance at 360 nm, whereas under the conditions $[\text{suc. acid}] > [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, when cerium has fully reacted, remaining succinic acid concentration was determined by titration with sodium hydroxide^{7a}. The main products were identified as cerium(III) and oxaloacetic acid (keto carboxylic acid). The results observed indicates that four moles of cerium(IV) reacts with one mole of succinic acid (Table 1) in accordance with eq. (1).

The product oxaloacetic acid (keto carboxylic acid) was identified by 2,4-DNP and sodium nitroprusside test⁸. The oxaloacetic acid was confirmed by IR spectra, which shows C=O stretching at 1700 cm^{-1} for carboxylic functional group and 1721 cm^{-1} for keto functional group.

Table 1. Stoichiometry of ruthenium(III) mediated succinic acid-cerium(IV) reaction at 25 °C

[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (Taken)	[suc. acid] × 10 ⁴ (Taken)	[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (Found)	[suc. acid] × 10 ⁴ (Found)
1.0	0.25	0.0	0.02
1.0	0.50	0.0	0.26
2.0	0.50	0.0	0.0
3.0	0.50	0.99	0.02
4.0	0.50	2.03	0.0
5.0	1.0	1.01	0.0

[Ru^{III}] = 5.0 × 10⁻⁶; [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 and *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³.

The product oxaloacetic acid was also confirmed by GC-mass spectral analysis. GC-MS data were obtained in a 17A Shimadzu gas chromatography with XP-5000A Shimadzu mass spectrometer using EI ionization technique. The mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at 131 amu confirming the presence of product oxaloacetic acid (Fig. 1). All other peaks absorbed in GC-MS can be interpreted in accordance with the observed structure of

oxaloacetic acid. The product cerium(III) was confirmed by UV-Vis spectra at 230 to 260 nm.

The reaction orders have been determined from the slopes of (rate)_c versus (concentration) plots by varying the concentrations of cerium(IV), succinic acid, sulphuric acid and ruthenium(III), in turn while keeping the others constant.

The oxidant cerium(IV) concentration was varied in the range of 5.0 × 10⁻⁵ – 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ and the order was found to be unity. The succinic acid concentration was varied in the concentration range 0.25 × 10⁻³ – 14.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of ruthenium(III), while keeping other reactant concentrations and conditions constant. It was observed that, the order with respect to succinic acid concentration was changed from first order to zero order as the succinic acid concentration increases (Fig. 2). In the lower concentration range, 0.25 × 10⁻³ to 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, the rate of oxidation shows first order dependence on succinic acid concentration. At intermediate concentration of succinic acid, 2.0 × 10⁻³ to 8.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ fractional order (0.46) dependence was observed and at high concentration (> 8.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) of succinic acid, the rate of oxidation is independent of succinic acid concentration. At constant oxidant, reductant and acid concentrations of 2.0 × 10⁻⁴, 5.0 × 10⁻³ and 0.50 mol dm⁻³ respectively, and *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³, the catalyst, ruthenium(III) concentration was varied between 1.0 × 10⁻⁶ and 1.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ (Table 2). The order with respect to ruthenium concentration was found to be unity. As catalyst concentration increases the rate of the reac-

Fig. 1. GC-MS spectra of the product oxaloacetic acid showed both molecular ion peak and base peak at *m/z* 131.

Fig. 2. Order with respect to succinic acid concentration.

Table 2. Effect of variation of cerium(IV), succinic acid, ruthenium(III) concentrations on ruthenium(III) mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C and $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[suc. acid] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ru ^{III}] × 10 ⁶ (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	(rate) _c × 10 ⁷ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	
				Found	Calcd.
0.5	5.0	5.0	0.50	1.21	1.23
1.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	2.43	2.46
2.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	4.92	4.92
3.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	7.23	7.38
4.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	9.82	9.84
5.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	12.3	12.3
2.0	0.25	5.0	0.50	0.43	-
2.0	0.50	5.0	0.50	0.86	-
2.0	1.0	5.0	0.50	1.72	1.72
2.0	2.0	5.0	0.50	3.10	2.95
2.0	4.0	5.0	0.50	4.41	4.41
2.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	4.92	4.92
2.0	6.0	5.0	0.50	5.32	5.33
2.0	8.0	5.0	0.50	5.96	5.95
2.0	10.0	5.0	0.50	6.40	6.39
2.0	12.0	5.0	0.50	6.37	-
2.0	14.0	5.0	0.50	6.45	-
2.0	5.0	0.0	0.50	0.60	-
2.0	5.0	1.0	0.50	0.98	0.98
2.0	5.0	2.0	0.50	1.95	1.96
2.0	5.0	3.0	0.50	2.93	2.95

Table-2 (cont.)

2.0	5.0	4.0	0.50	3.91	3.93
2.0	5.0	5.0	0.50	4.92	4.92
2.0	5.0	6.0	0.50	5.90	5.90
2.0	5.0	7.0	0.50	6.81	6.88
2.0	5.0	8.0	0.50	7.85	7.87
2.0	5.0	9.0	0.50	8.83	8.85
2.0	5.0	10.0	0.50	9.84	9.84

tion also increases (Fig. 3), and activity of catalyst reaches a maximum after $[Ru^{III}] \geq 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ under the above mentioned experimental conditions. Under the condition used the initial rate for uncatalyzed $(rate)_u = 5.95 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is negligible compared to the

mediated reaction (Table 2).

At fixed concentrations of $[Ru^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ with other conditions remaining constant, the initial rate was found to decrease with increasing sulphuric acid concentration (Table 3). The *in situ* H^+ ion concentra-

Fig. 3. Effect of catalyst, Ru^{III} on the oxidation of succinic acid by Ce^{IV} in aqueous H_2SO_4 medium at $25^\circ C$: $[Ce^{IV}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$; $[succ. acid] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$; $[H_2SO_4] = 0.50$; $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Table 3. Variation of different cerium(IV) species^a with $[H^+]$ on ruthenium(III) mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in acid medium at $25^\circ C$

$[H_2SO_4]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[H_2SO_4^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[H^+]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[SO_4^{2-}]$	$10^3 \alpha_O$	α_{OH}	$10 \alpha_1$	$10^2 \alpha_2$	$10^2 \alpha_3$	$10^2 \alpha_4$	$(rate)_c \times 10^7$ (mol dm^{-3})	
										Found	Calcd.
0.1	0.175	0.0247	0.857	1.758	0.1749	5.805	21.939	2.296	1.220	6.98	6.98
0.2	0.340	0.059	0.692	1.616	0.4089	4.303	13.129	2.670	1.084	6.61	6.61
0.3	0.490	0.109	0.542	2.421	0.3329	5.048	12.061	3.534	3.805	6.12	6.13
0.4	0.619	0.180	0.413	3.505	0.2913	5.575	10.159	3.756	8.445	5.55	5.55
0.5	0.721	0.278	0.311	4.971	0.2675	5.961	8.189	3.525	1.423	4.92	4.92

Table-3 (contd.)

0.6	0.795	0.404	0.237	6.842	0.2539	6.242	6.253	3.095	1.876	4.30	4.29
0.7	0.847	0.552	0.185	9.018	0.2450	6.419	5.234	2.672	2.493	3.74	3.73
0.8	0.884	0.715	0.148	11.435	0.2396	6.545	4.292	2.265	2.882	3.27	3.26
0.9	0.905	0.894	0.127	13.599	0.2279	6.691	3.771	1.844	3.318	2.87	2.86
1.0	0.928	1.071	0.104	16.643	0.2330	6.684	3.075	1.704	3.410	2.56	2.55

$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$; $[\text{suc. acid}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$; $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$; $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

α_{O} , α_{OH} , α_1 , α_2 , α_3 and α_4 are the fractions of total cerium(IV) of species Ce^{4+} , $[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]$, $[\text{CeSO}_4^{2+}]$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]$, $[\text{HCe}(\text{SO}_4)_3^-]$ and $[\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-]$, respectively.

tion in the sulphuric acid-sulphate media was calculated using the known ionization constant of acid sulphate as in an earlier study^{3,9}. From the plot of $(\text{rate})_c$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$, the order with respect to H^+ ion concentration was

found to be negative and less than unity. Cerium(IV) is known to form several complexes in acid sulphate media^{3,5} such as CeSO_4^{2+} , $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2\text{HSO}_4^-$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ as shown in equilibria (3)–(6). The total cerium(IV) concentration is the sum of different cerium(IV) species concentrations, $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]$, $[\text{CeSO}_4^{2+}]$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]$, $[\text{HCe}(\text{SO}_4)_3^-]$ and $[\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-]$, the complexes having the cumulative equilibrium constants, K_{OH} , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 and β_4 as shown in eq. (7).

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t = [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_{\text{OH}}}{[\text{H}^+]} + \beta_1[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2[\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2[\text{HSO}_4^-]^2[\text{H}^+] \right\} \quad (7)$$

where, $K_{\text{OH}} = 15$, $\beta_1 = 3.85 \times 10^2$, $\beta_2 = 1.69 \times 10^2$, $\beta_3 = 1.01 \times 10^2$ and $\beta_4 = 2.03 \times 10^2$.

The approximate concentrations of cerium sulphate complexes can be calculated from the concentrations of dissolved Ce^{4+} , H^+ , HSO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} from the equilibria and their constants^{3,5}. The results of such calculations

are utilized to draw Fig. 4. From the Fig. 4 it is clear that, in the presence of ruthenium(III), among the concentrations of different cerium(IV) species, the variation of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ with H^+ ion concentration shows only parallelism with the variation of rate with H^+ ion concentration. Hence, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ species is considered as the active species of oxidant.

The effect of initially added product, cerium(III) was studied in the 5.0×10^{-5} – $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration range, keeping the ionic strength, reactant concentration and other concentration constant. It was found that cerium(III) in the concentration range 5.0×10^{-5} – $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ caused a decrease in rate, whereas, for similar range of added oxaloacetic acid, the rate did not change appreciably. The inhibitory effect of initially added product, cerium(III) is shown in Fig. 5.

Rates of reaction with 30 different sets of concentration of cerium(IV), succinic acid, ruthenium(III), $[\text{H}^+]$ and cerium(III) at constant ionic strength were found to obey the rate law (8) as shown in Fig. 6.

$$(\text{rate})_c = \frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{8.2979 \times 10^4 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{suc. acid}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{0.58 + [\text{H}^+] + 233 [\text{suc. acid}] [\text{H}^+] + 135.14 [\text{suc. acid}]} \quad (8)$$

At constant concentration and at other constant conditions, as the concentration of sulphate and bisulphate ions increased, the rate of reaction decreased. The decrease in rate constant due to sulphate ion concentration is much more than that due to bisulphate ion concentration.

At constant concentrations of reactants and catalyst and other conditions constant, the ionic strength was varied by varying the concentration of sodium sulphate be-

Fig. 4. Effect of acid concentration on different cerium(IV) species and also on the rate (conditions as in Table 3).

Fig. 5. Plot of $1/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $[Ce^{III}]$: $[Ce^{IV}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$; [suc. acid] = 5.0×10^{-3} ; $[H_2SO_4] = 0.5$; $[Ru^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$; $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

tween 1.60 and 3.20 mol dm⁻³ and (rate)_c was found to increase with increasing ionic strength. A plot of (rate)_c versus $I^{1/2}$ is linear with positive slope (Fig. 7). At con-

stant acidity and other constant conditions, as the ethanoic acid content increases from 0 to 50% (v/v) in the reaction mixture, the reaction rate decreases. Since the dielectric

Fig. 6. Plot of the initial rate, $(rate)_c$ of Ce^{IV} -succinic acid reaction versus the product of reactant concentrations at 25 °C and $I = 1.60$ mol dm^{-3} .

Fig. 7. Effect of variation of dielectric constant (D) and ionic strength (I) on the ruthenium(III) mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in aqueous acid medium at 25 °C.

constants of aqueous ethanoic acid are not available in the reaction mixture, they were computed from the pure liquid values¹⁰. No reaction of the solvent with the oxidant occurred under the experimental conditions employed. A plot of $\log(\text{rate})_c$ versus $1/D$ was linear with negative slope (Fig. 7).

The intervention of free radicals was examined as follows. The reaction mixture, to which a known quantity of acrylonitrile scavenger had been added initially, was kept in an inert atmosphere for 6 h. Upon diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, precipitate resulted suggesting the participation of free radicals in the reaction.

In presence of ruthenium(III), the kinetics was studied at 15, 25, 35 and 45 °C. As the temperature increased the initial rate also increased. The results are given in Table 4. The rate constant, k for slow step of Scheme 1 were obtained from the intercept and slopes of the plot of

Table 4. (a) Effect of temperature on ruthenium(III) mediated oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium. Rate constant with respect to slow step of Scheme 1

Temp. (K)	$k \times 10^2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
288	9.96
298	13.54
308	18.26
318	24.65
Parameters	Values
Activation parameters	
E_a	$23 \pm 1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$
ΔH^\ddagger	$21 \pm 1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$
ΔS^\ddagger	$-116 \pm 4 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
ΔG^\ddagger	$55 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$
$\log A$	7 ± 0.02

(b) Effect of temperature on first and second step of Scheme 1.

Temp. (K)	K_5 (mol dm^{-3})	K_6 ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1}$)
298	0.64	269
303	0.58	233
308	0.53	167
313	0.47	140
Thermodynamic quantities	Values from K_5	Values from K_6
ΔH	-7.7	-17.4 kJ mol^{-1}
ΔS	-30.6	-13.9 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
ΔG	2.00	-13.1 kJ mol^{-1}

$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $1/[\text{suc. acid}]$ (Fig. 8) and $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 8), at four different temperatures (Table 4). The energy of activation was obtained by the plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ from which the activation parameters were calculated (Table 4). Ionization constant (K_5) of the step of Scheme 1 was evaluated from (intercept)/(slope) of plot $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ at four different temperatures. Similarly the formation constant (K_6) of the complex second step of Scheme 1 was obtained from (intercept)/(slope) of the plot of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $1/[\text{suc. acid}]$ at four different temperatures. The van't Hoff plots ($\log K_5$ versus $1/T$ and $\log K_6$ versus $1/D$) were drawn at four different temperatures. The thermodynamic quantities were calculated and are given in Table 4.

The cerium(IV) oxidation of succinic acid is slow in aqueous sulphuric acid, under the experimental conditions studied, the initial rate is $5.95 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. However, the reaction occurs with reasonable rates in the presence of micro amounts of ruthenium(III) ($10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in aqueous sulphuric acid. Hence the reaction was taken in sulphuric acid. The reaction between cerium(IV) and of succinic acid in presence of ruthenium(III) in aqueous sulphuric acid has a stoichiometry 1 : 4. The order with respect to cerium(IV) concentrations was found to be unity. But, the order with respect to succinic acid concentration varies from first order to zero order as the succinic acid concentration increases. The effect of hydrogen ions on the rate of reaction was studied by adding sulphuric acid and it was found that, as the sulphuric acid concentration increases in reaction mixture, the rate of reaction decreased. This is due to the formation¹¹ of active inhibitor $\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$. The order with respect to H^+ concentration was found to be less than unity and negative. As the sulphuric acid concentration increased in the reaction mixture, the H^+ ion concentration increases, but there is also a corresponding increase in HSO_4^- ion concentration to a great extent. The overall effect of adding sulphuric acid would be to lower the rate (Table 3). A similar behavior has been reported in the oxidation of antimony(III)³, mandelic acid¹¹, malic acid¹², and fructose¹³ and L-glutamic acid¹⁴ by cerium(IV). Added cerium(III) retards the reaction due to formation of $\text{Ce}^{4+} \cdot \text{Ce}^{3+}$ ion pairs. In the oxidation of tellurium(IV) by cerium(IV), the product cerium(III), also retards the reac-

Fig. 8. Verification of rate law (14) in the form of (15) (conditions as in Tables 2 and 3).

tion^{15,16}. The experimental results suggest that succinic acid combines with catalyst to form a complex, which then reacts in a slow step with one mole of cerium(IV) to give product cerium(III), a free radical derived from succinic acid, with regeneration of catalyst ruthenium. This free radical formed reacts with another mole of cerium(IV) in a further fast step to give the product cerium(III) and malic acid. Further, malic acid combines with another mole of cerium(IV) to form free radical derived from malic acid and cerium(III). Free radical derived from malic acid reacts with another mole of cerium(IV) to form the products oxaloacetic acid [keto-carboxylic acid] and cerium(III). The results are accommodated in Scheme 1.

The results indicate the formation of complex between substrate and catalyst. The spectral evidence for a complex formation between substrate and catalyst was obtained from UV-Vis spectra of succinic acid and succinic acid-ruthenium mixtures in which a bathochromic shift of 4 nm from 322 nm to 326 nm and hypochromicity at 326 nm was observed. The formation of complex was also proved kinetically by a non-zero intercept of the plot $[Ce^{IV}][Ru^{III}]/(rate)_c$ versus $1/[suc. acid]$ (Fig. 8). Such complex formation between substrate and catalyst has been observed in literature¹⁷. Scheme 1 leads to the following

rate law (14) which explains the observed order in cerium(IV), succinic acid, H^+ and ruthenium(III). The derived rate law is applicable for intermediate concentration of succinic acid.

$$\begin{aligned} (rate)_c &= k [\text{Complex}] [Ce^{IV}] \\ &= \frac{k K_5 K_6 [Ce^{IV}] [suc. acid] [Ru^{III}]}{[H^+]} \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

The total concentration of succinic acid, $[suc. acid]_t$ is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} [suc. acid]_t &= [suc. acid]_f + C \\ &= [suc. acid]_f + K_6 [suc. acid]_f [Ru^{III}] \\ &= [suc. acid]_f \{1 + K_6 [Ru^{III}]\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[suc. acid]_f = \frac{[suc. acid]_t}{1 + K_6 [Ru^{III}]} \quad (10)$$

where subscripts *t* and *f* stands for total and free respectively.

But, in the experiment very low concentration of ruthenium(III) is used. Hence, the term $K_6 [Ru^{III}]$ may be neglected in comparison with unity in eq. (10).

Scheme 1

So,

$$[\text{suc. acid}]_f = [\text{suc. acid}]_t$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t &= [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_f + K_6 [\text{suc. acid}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \\
 &= [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_f \{1 + K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_f = \frac{[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t}{1 + K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 (11) \quad [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t &= [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f + [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{H}^+] \\
 &= [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f + K_5 \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f}{[\text{H}^+]} \\
 &= [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f + \left\{1 + \frac{K_5}{[\text{H}^+]}\right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

(12) Therefore,

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t}{1 + K_5/[\text{H}^+]} \quad (13)$$

Substituting eqs. (11), (12) and (13) in eq. (9) and omitting the subscripts, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{rate})_c &= \frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k K_5 K_6 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{suc. acid}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_5 + K_6 [\text{suc. acid}][\text{H}^+] + K_5 K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The rate law (14) may be rearranged to eq. (15) which is suitable for verification

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{(\text{rate})_c} &= \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k K_5 K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]} + \\ &\frac{1}{k K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k K_5} + \frac{1}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

According to eq. (15) the plots of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $1/[\text{suc. acid}]$ and $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ should be linear and are found to be so (Fig. 8).

(I) From the first plot, i.e. $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $1/[\text{suc. acid}]$

$$(\text{Slope})_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k K_5 K_6} + \frac{1}{k K_6} \quad (16)$$

$$(\text{Intercept})_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k K_5} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (17)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(\text{Intercept})_1}{(\text{Slope})_1} &= K_6 \\ &= \text{Formation constant of the complex (C}_1\text{)} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

(II) From the second plot, i.e. $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/(\text{rate})_c$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{Slope})_2 &= \frac{1}{k K_5 K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]} + \frac{1}{k K_5} \\ &= \frac{1}{k K_5} \left\{ \frac{1 + K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]}{K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$(\text{Intercept})_2 = \frac{1}{k K_5 [\text{suc. acid}]} + \frac{1}{k}$$

$$= \frac{1}{k} \left\{ \frac{1 + K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]}{K_6 [\text{suc. acid}]} \right\} \quad (20)$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(\text{Intercept})_2}{(\text{Slope})_2} &= K_5 \\ &= \text{Ionisation constant of } \text{Ce}^{4+} \cdot \text{H}^+ \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Substituting the values of K_5 and $[\text{H}^+]$ in the (intercept)₁ of the first plot, i.e. in the eq. (17) we get the value of k , the rate constant with respect to the slow step of Scheme 1. By this procedure the obtained values of k , K_5 and K_6 are $13.54 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $0.58 \pm \text{mol dm}^{-3}$ and $233 \pm \text{dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The value of K_5 obtained is in reasonable agreement with literature¹⁵ ($K_5 = 0.56$). Using these values, the rate under different experimental conditions were calculated and compared with experimental data. The experimental and calculated values agree reasonably well (Tables 2 and 3).

The active species involved in the mechanism can be understood as follows : The variation of the rate with acidity is shown in the "results section", to parallel the trend of variation of concentration of the $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ species with the acidity (Table 3, Fig. 4). Hence, it is confirmed that $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ is the active species of oxidant. The use of RuCl_3 as homogeneous catalyst in both acidic and alkaline media is of recent interest. In dilute acid and chloride solutions the salt yields complex ions¹⁸, such as $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$, $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{Cl}_2]^+$, $[\text{RuCl}_6]^{3-}$, $[\text{RuCl}_4]^-$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_4]^-$. The existence of such complexes seems to be remote due to presence of micro amounts of chloride in reaction media. The electronic spectrum of ruthenium(III) indicates $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ is the active species of ruthenium(III) in acid media¹⁹. Hence $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ has been considered to be active species of ruthenium(III) under our experimental conditions. The mechanism of Scheme 1 will therefore involve these species as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The rate law eq. (14) can be written in the following form

$$(\text{rate})_c = \frac{k K_8 K_9 [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] [\text{suc. acid}]}{[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+} \left([\text{H}_+] + K_8 + K_9 [\text{suc. acid}] [\text{H}^+] + K_8 K_9 [\text{suc. acid}] \right)} \quad (22)$$

But,

$$\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 = \beta_2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 \quad (23)$$

From eq. (7), we have,

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_f = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t}{1 + K_{\text{OH}}/[\text{H}^+] + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] [\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-] [\text{H}^+]} \quad (24)$$

$$\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 = \frac{\beta_2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2}{1 + K_{\text{OH}}/[\text{H}^+] + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] [\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-] [\text{H}^+]} \quad (25)$$

According to step 3 of Scheme 2

$$[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+} = K_9 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (26)$$

Substituting eq. (25) and eq. (26) in eq. (22), we have

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{\beta_2 k K_8 K_9 K_{10} [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2}{[\text{D-mannitol}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \times \frac{1}{[\text{H}^+] + K_8 + K_{10} [\text{D-mannitol}]} \times \frac{1}{[\text{A}]} \quad (27)$$

where, $[\text{A}] = 1 + K_{\text{OH}}/[\text{H}^+] + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] [\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-] [\text{H}^+]$.

The effect of ionic strength was in the right direction since two ions having the same charged species are involved in Scheme 1. The effect of solvent on reaction rate has been described in literature²⁰. The increase in the ethanoic acid content in the reaction medium leads to decrease in the rate of reaction, which is in contrary to that expected for a reaction between positively charged species and a neutral molecule in the medium of lower dielectric constant. Perhaps this effect is countered substantially by the formation of active reactant species to a greater extent in the high dielectric constant, leading to a net increase in the rate. The modest activation energy and sizable entropy of activation support a complex transition state in the reaction.

The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were both favorable for electron transfer processes. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger indicates that complex (C₁) is more ordered than the reactants²¹. The values of ΔS^\ddagger is within the range of radical reaction and has been ascribed²² to the nature of electron

pairing and unpairing process and to the loss of degree of freedom formerly available to reactants upon the formation of rigid transition state. The observed modest enthalpy of activation and a relatively low value of the entropy of activation as well as higher value of the rate constant of the slow step indicates that the oxidation presumably occur via an inner-sphere mechanism. This conclusion is supported by literature²³.

The reaction between cerium(IV) and succinic acid is slow in sulphuric acid medium at room temperature. The reaction occurs with measurable velocity in the presence of minute quantity ($\sim 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³) of ruthenium(III). The main active species of cerium(IV) is considered as Ce(SO₄)₂, although other species might be active to much lesser extent and [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺ is considered as the active species of the catalyst, ruthenium(III). The role of hydrogen ion is crucial to the reaction. The description of the mechanism is consistent with all the experimental evidence.

Experimental

The solutions are prepared in H₂O, which had been twice distilled in an all-glass unit in the presence of potassium permanganate. Reagent grade chemicals were used. A stock solution of succinic acid (s.d fine chem) was prepared by dissolving in water and standardized by titration against sodium hydroxide^{7a}. Cerium(IV) stock solution was obtained by dissolving cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate (E. Merck) in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ of H₂SO₄ and standardized with iron(II) ammonium sulphate solution^{7b}. Commercial RuCl₃.nH₂O contains other oxidation states of Ru; such as Ru^{II}, Ru^{IV}. It should be repeatedly digested with conc. HCl to convert it to Ru^{III}. Cerium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving cerium(III) sulphate (BDH) in water. Na₂SO₄ (AR) and H₂SO₄ (AR) were used to provide the required ionic strength and acidity, respectively.

All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with [suc. acid] > [Ce^{IV}] at constant ionic strength of 1.60 mol dm⁻³. The reaction was initiated by mixing the normally equilibrated (25.0 ± 0.1 °C) solution of cerium(IV), succinic acid and ruthenium(III), which also contained the required quantity of sulphuric acid and sodium sulphate. The reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of cerium(IV)

in the mixture at 360 nm in 1 cm cell placed in the thermostatted compartment of a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-vis spectrophotometer. Beer's law has been verified between 2.0×10^{-5} and 6.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ of cerium(IV) at 360 nm under the reaction conditions ($\epsilon = 3500 \pm 50$ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). In the present study one of the product cerium(III) retards the reaction, hence initial rates were determined from [Ce^{IV}] versus time plot. The initial rates, (rate)_c obtained were reproducible within ± 5% and are the average of at least four independent kinetic runs (Table 2).

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